

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

BLOCKING THE OPERATION OF CURRENT PROTECTION AGAINST STARTING CURRENTS OF ELECTRIC MOTORS BASED ON THE RESULTS OF THE ANALYSIS OF INSTANTANEOUS POWER VALUES

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ABSTRACT

In the system of protection of power grids against short-circuit currents, the starting currents of electric motors are an undesirable interference that can be eliminated by blocking the operation of protection against these currents. Identification of inrush currents can be carried out by analyzing the value of the power factor of the electrical circuit. A method has been developed for quickly determining the value of the power factor based on the analysis of only two instantaneous values of the power, which are achieved 5 and 15 ms after the moment of disturbance of the circuit (starting the electric motor or short circuit).

It is shown that the presence in circuit breakers of the function of identification and blocking of inrush currents makes it possible to build such a system of protection against short-circuit currents, which provides both protection against remote short-circuits and protection redundancy of failures of feeder switches by input switches.

Keywords: instantaneous power, inrush currents.

When building protection of electrical networks against short-circuit currents (SC), the inrush currents of electric motors (EM) are essentially an unwanted hindrance that reduces the sensitivity and reliability of protection. Since the inrush current of an EM close to the current source can be greater than the remote SC at the end of a long line, the current setting of the circuit breaker has to be chosen larger than the value of the expected remote SC. Therefore, the presence of inrush currents does not make it possible to realize protection against short-circuit currents.

The starting currents in the feeder lines do not allow the installation of such small current settings in the input switch, which, in the event of a failure of the feeder switch, will protect the line behind it with an input switch. This means that the inrush currents of the EM interfere with the redundancy of feeder switch failures.

Thus, to increase the reliability of protection against SC, it is advisable to eliminate the disturbance in the form of inrush currents of the EM. This can be done by blocking the tripping of protection against inrush currents, if the problem of reliable identification of these currents is solved.

It is possible to identify the type of perturbation current of an electric circuit by the value of the power factor - $\cos \varphi$. It is known that the time constant of the windings of electric motor windings corresponds to the values of power factor $\cos \varphi = (0,2 \div 0,3)$, while the time constant of cable and overhead lines corresponds to the values of $\cos \varphi = (0,7 \div 0,8)$. Therefore, to identify the inrush current, a methodology for quick determination of the value $\cos \varphi$ of the circuit with the disturbance

current is necessary. The need for a quick determination of the value $\cos \varphi$ is due to the fact that with an increase in the speed of rotation of the ED, the value $\cos \varphi$ increases. Therefore, the determination of the magnitude $\cos \varphi$ must be carried out in a very short period of time after the start of the EM, while its rotor remains practically stationary. It means that it is expedient to determine the value $\cos \varphi$ not after the end of the transient process of starting current change, but directly in the process of its change. But, as you know, the nature of the change in the value of the current in the transient mode depends not only $\cos \varphi$ on (or τ), but also on the moment of time of occurrence of the perturbation current. Dependence on the moment of current occurrence time is due to the fact that in the steady-state mode the current value is not a constant value, but varies with time increases with increasing speed of rotation of the electric motor.

Therefore, to extract information about the value $\cos \varphi$ it is necessary to analyze the transient process of change of such a parameter of the electric circuit, the value of which in steady state will be constant.

One of these parameters, as is known [1], is the total of all three phases of the active power - $P = 3UI \cos \varphi$. Therefore, the nature of the change in the specified power $P(t)$ in the transient mode will depend only on the value of $\cos \varphi$ (or τ). Let us analyze the analytical expression of the total power $P(t)$.

The active power in phases a, b, and c in transient mode are as follows:

$$p_a(t) = 2UI \sin(\omega t + \psi) \left[\sin(\omega t + \psi - \varphi) - \sin(\psi - \varphi) e^{-t/\tau} \right] \quad (1)$$

$$p_b(t) = 2UI \sin(\omega t + \psi + 2\pi/3) \left[\sin(\omega t + \psi - \varphi + 2\pi/3) - \sin(\psi - \varphi + 2\pi/3) e^{-t/\tau} \right] \quad (2)$$

$$p_c(t) = 2UI \sin(\omega t + \psi - 2\pi/3) \left[\sin(\omega t + \psi - \varphi - 2\pi/3) - \sin(\psi - \varphi - 2\pi/3) e^{-t/\tau} \right] \quad (3)$$

where: U and I - respectively, the effective values of phase voltage and current, τ - the electromagnetic time constant of the circuit, ψ - the initial phase of the circuit disturbance occurrence.

As follows from the expressions (1)-(3), the instantaneous values of the phase powers depend on both τ (and hence $\cos\varphi$) and the angle ψ . This means that it is impossible to extract information about the magnitude $\cos\varphi$ from instantaneous power values in one phase. We show that such information can be extracted if we analyze the total instantaneous power for all three phases. Omitting all intermediate transformations of the sum of expressions (1)-(3), we give the final expression for the total instantaneous power in the transient mode when measuring the capacities in each of the 3 phases - $P(t)$.

$$P(t) = 3UI \left[\cos\varphi - \cos(\omega t + \varphi) e^{-t/\tau} \right] \quad (4)$$

Analysis of expressions (4) shows that the character of change of function $P(t)$ at the beginning of the transient process has the form of damped oscillations relative to the steady-state value.

Fig. 1 shows, as an example, the dependences $P(t)$ plotted by expression (4) for two values of $\cos\varphi$ - for $\cos\varphi=0.2$ and $\cos\varphi=0.7$. As can be seen from the above graphs, the values of the "range" of change in the instantaneous total power from its maximum value P_{\max} to the minimum value P_{\min} at two values of $\cos\varphi$ differ significantly. Thus, the value of the "range" of extreme values at $\cos\varphi=0.2$ is more than 5 times greater than the similar "range" of extreme values of total power for $\cos\varphi=0.7$. This means that the analysis of extreme values of the total instantaneous power (P_{\max} and P_{\min}) allows you to quickly and accurately estimate the value $\cos\varphi$, and therefore identify the starting current of the EM.

Fig.1 Dependencies of $P(t)$ at different values of $\cos\varphi$

It is necessary to note an interesting feature of the nature of the function $P(t)$, which makes it possible to significantly simplify the algorithm for determining the value $\cos\varphi$. As shown by the analysis of the function $P(t)$ for extremes, the maximum values P_{\max} always occur after 5 ms, and the minimum values P_{\min} after 15 ms after the occurrence of the perturbation current, regardless of the magnitude $\cos\varphi$.

The most informative parameter characterizing the "span" of the function $P(t)$ at different values of

$\cos\varphi$, is the ratio of the difference of extreme power values to their sum:

$$K_p = \frac{P_{\max} - P_{\min}}{P_{\max} + P_{\min}} \quad (5)$$

And taking into account the fact that the values P_{\max} are reached in 5 ms, and the values P_{\min} in 15 ms after the moment of starting the EM, the expression (6) can be represented as:

$$K_p = \frac{P_5 - P_{15}}{P_5 + P_{15}} \quad (6),$$

where $P_5 = P_{\max}$ and $P_{15} = \pm P_{\min}$.

In fig. 2 shows the dependence $K_p = f(\cos\varphi)$ from which it follows that the values $\cos\varphi$ significantly depend on the value of the

coefficient K_p . So, when starting EM, when $\cos\varphi = (0.2 \div 0.4)$ value K_p is in the range $K_p = (0.45 \div 1.5)$, while at short circuit the value K_p is in the range $K_p = (0.08 \div 0.12)$. This indicates that the coefficient K_p , indeed, can be a reliable criterion for identifying the inrush current.

Fig.2 Dependence of the coefficient K_p on the value of $\cos\varphi$

The algorithm of operation of the microprocessor release in the implementation of the function of blocking starting currents based on the analysis of the nature of the change in time of active power is shown in Fig.3.

In module 1 the data of the excitation current of the electric circuit Δi_j are extracted from the general signal from current sensors. In module 2 discrete values of voltages Δu_j are determined, and in module 3 discrete values of power P_j are determined. In module 4, the power value at time moments 5 and 15 ms after

current occurrence - values (P_5 and P_{15}) are determined. Module 5 determines the value of the coefficient K_p , and module 6 determines the value of $\cos\varphi$ from the dependence $\cos\varphi = f(K_p)$. In module 7, the value $\cos\varphi$ is compared with the permissible value and if the inequality $\cos\varphi \leq 0.5$ is fulfilled, a signal is generated to block tripping of the protection.

Fig. 3 Algorithm for implementing the function of blocking starting currents based on power analysis

Realization of the function of blocking the tripping of protection against inrush currents of electric motors makes it possible to ignore the presence of electric motors in these networks when building protection of electric networks. In this case, when protecting a long line, the current set point of the protective device can be set not more than the value of the short-circuit current at the end of the line, despite the fact that the inrush current of the motor close to the current source may be greater in magnitude. This means that protection against remote short-circuit currents will be provided.

In branched electrical networks, the current setpoint of the input switch can be selected equal to the minimum current setpoint of one of the feeder switches, although the total value of the starting currents of the ED in the feeder lines may be greater. This ensures redundancy of feeder switch failures

Resume. The possibility of a significant increase in the reliability of protection of electrical networks from short-circuit currents by eliminating unwanted interference in the form of starting currents of electric motors is shown. For this purpose, a method is proposed for reliable identification of inrush currents to block the operation of protection when they occur. In

it, as a criterion for identifying the starting current, the power factor of the circuit with the disturb current is used, the method for identifying the starting current is based on the analysis of discrete values of the total active power of the three phases. The main advantage of this method of identifying the starting current is its simplicity. Essentially, it is necessary to determine only two instantaneous power values - 5 and 15 ms after the occurrence of the circuit disturbance current

References

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